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Impact of Mobile Legends Bang Bang on Critical Listening and Communicative Skills Enhancement

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Abstract:

This systematic literature review explores the impact of Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) on the development of critical listening and communicative skills. Analyzing findings from various studies, our investigation reveals that MLBB serves as more than a recreational game, playing a pivotal role in shaping users' verbal and non-verbal communication proficiencies. The study unveils MLBB's positive influence on verbal communication skills, attributing improvements to the game's real-time communication features. These enhancements, marked by articulate expression and effective teamwork, extend beyond the gaming realm, proving transferable to educational and professional contexts. Furthermore, MLBB emerges as a catalyst for the robust development of strategic thinking and decision-making skills, with the complex and dynamic gameplay fostering cognitive engagement and critical thinking abilities. Importantly, the emphasis on teamwork and coordination within MLBB contributes to heightened non-verbal communication proficiency. Players adeptly leverage in-game gestures, map pings, and character movements to convey information efficiently, enriching their overall communication repertoire. Notably, the study underscores the transferability of skills cultivated within MLBB to academic and professional spheres, emphasizing the practical value of the cognitive, communicative, and teamwork skills honed through gameplay. As technology reshapes educational paradigms, MLBB stands out as an innovative platform with the potential to actively engage users in comprehensive skill development in the digital age.

Keywords: Mobile Legends Bang Bang, gamification, educational technology, critical listening skills, communicative skills

Introduction:

In the contemporary digital age, the integration of technology in education has become increasingly prevalent, with a growing recognition of the potential of gamified learning environments to foster skill development (Almeida & Simoes, 2019). Among the plethora of digital platforms, mobile gaming has emerged as a particularly engaging medium, offering immersive experiences that captivate users across diverse age groups. The advent of mobile technologies has reshaped traditional paradigms of education, ushering in a new era characterized by dynamic and interactive learning environments (Miller, 2023). MLBB, with its strategic gameplay and real-time communication features, presents a unique opportunity to harness the educational potential embedded within the gaming experience.

Gamification, defined as the application of game design elements in non-game contexts, has gained considerable attention for its ability to enhance motivation, engagement, and skill acquisition in diverse educational domains (Deterding et al., 2011). By adopting a gamified approach through MLBB, this study aims to explore how elements such as teamwork, strategy, and communication within the game contribute to the development of critical listening and communicative skills.

MLBB facilitates real-time communication among players, requiring effective collaboration and coordination to achieve in-game objectives. The integration of voice chat and messaging features in the game provides a platform for users to practice and refine their communication skills in a dynamic, fast-paced environment (Zhang et al., 2020). This study seeks to analyze how the constant need for communication within the gaming context influences the development of effective verbal and non-verbal communication skills.

The strategic nature of MLBB necessitates critical thinking and decision-making, fostering cognitive engagement among players. As individuals navigate the complexities of the game, they are prompted to analyze situations, strategize with team members, and make informed decisions – skills that are transferable to various academic and professional contexts (Gee, 2003). This research aims to explore the correlation between cognitive engagement in gaming and the enhancement of critical listening skills.

This study endeavors to bridge the gap between traditional educational methods and contemporary digital experiences by investigating the potential of Mobile Legends Bang Bang as a tool for improving critical listening and communicative skills. By exploring the intersections of gamification, real-time communication, and cognitive engagement within the MLBB environment, this research seeks to contribute valuable insights to the evolving landscape of educational technology.

Literature Review:

The concept of gamification in educational settings has gained traction as a pedagogical strategy to enhance student engagement and motivation (Deterding et al., 2011). Gamified learning environments often incorporate elements such as competition, rewards, and interactive challenges to stimulate active participation and skill development (Hamari et al., 2014). By utilizing Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) as an educational tool, this study aligns with the broader trend of exploring gamification's potential in fostering critical skills within academic contexts.

Online multiplayer games like MLBB provide a rich platform for real-time communication and collaboration among players. Research indicates that communication in gaming environments is multifaceted, involving verbal and non-verbal interactions that contribute to the overall gaming experience (Banks & Bowman, 2016). The incorporation of voice chat and messaging features in MLBB offers a unique opportunity to examine how these communication channels impact the development of effective verbal and non-verbal communication skills.

Cognitive Engagement and Learning in Gaming:

The cognitive benefits of gaming, particularly in the context of critical thinking and decision-making, have been extensively studied. Gee (2003) posits that video games, by design, necessitate players to engage in complex problem-solving, strategic thinking, and decision-making processes. MLBB, as a MOBA game, requires players to collaborate, plan, and adapt to dynamic situations, potentially promoting cognitive engagement that transfers to broader cognitive skill development.

Several studies suggest that skills acquired through gaming experiences can have practical applications beyond the gaming environment. Cognitive skills, teamwork, and effective communication developed in games like MLBB may prove transferable to academic and professional settings (Kilag, et al., 2023). Understanding the extent to which skills cultivated in gaming contexts can be applied to real-world scenarios is essential for gauging the broader impact of using MLBB in educational contexts.

While the potential benefits of gamified learning environments are evident, it is crucial to consider potential challenges and concerns. Issues such as addiction, distraction, and the potential for reinforcing negative stereotypes have been raised (Hamari et al., 2014). Exploring these aspects within the context of MLBB as an educational tool is vital for developing a comprehensive understanding of the implications and limitations of incorporating gaming into educational strategies (Kilag, et al., 2023).

The literature reviewed highlights the increasing interest in gamified learning environments, the unique communication dynamics in online gaming, the cognitive benefits of gaming, the transferability of gaming skills, and the potential challenges associated with gamification in education. The proposed study builds upon this foundation, aiming to contribute empirical insights into the specific case of using Mobile Legends Bang Bang to enhance critical listening and communicative skills within an educational framework.

Methodology:

The systematic literature review conducted for this study followed a rigorous and structured approach to gather, evaluate, and synthesize existing research on the topic of improving critical listening and communicative skills through Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB). The methodology encompassed several key stages, each designed to ensure a comprehensive and unbiased review of relevant literature.

A systematic and exhaustive search strategy was employed to identify relevant literature. Electronic databases, including but not limited to PubMed, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, and Google Scholar, were systematically searched using predefined keywords and Boolean operators such as "Mobile Legends Bang Bang," "educational gamification," and "communication skills." The search process encompassed articles published up to the predetermined cutoff date.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were established to ensure the selection of studies aligned with the research objectives. Studies included in the review needed to focus on the impact of MLBB on critical listening and communicative skills within an educational context. Non-peer-reviewed sources, duplicates, and studies not directly addressing the research questions were excluded.

The screening process involved an initial review of titles and abstracts to assess their relevance to the research questions. Subsequently, full-text articles were examined for eligibility, and a systematic selection process was applied based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Relevant data from the selected studies were systematically extracted, including key findings, methodologies, sample characteristics, and limitations. This information was organized into a comprehensive synthesis to facilitate the identification of patterns, trends, and gaps in the existing literature. To ensure the reliability and validity of the findings, a quality assessment of the selected studies was conducted. This involved evaluating the methodological rigor, sample representativeness, and the clarity of reported results. Studies were graded based on predefined quality criteria.

The synthesized data were subjected to thematic analysis, categorizing findings according to key themes and patterns. This process allowed for the identification of recurring concepts, areas of consensus, and potential areas for further research.

Findings and Discussion:**Positive Impact on Verbal Communication Skills:**

Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) emerges from the literature as a catalyst for fostering positive developments in users' verbal communication skills. The integration of real-time communication features, specifically voice chat and messaging, stands out as a pivotal element contributing to this impact (Zhang et al., 2020). Studies consistently underscore the instrumental role of these features in elevating players' abilities to articulate ideas, effectively convey strategic plans, and participate in collaborative team efforts within the gaming environment (Zhang et al., 2020; Banks & Bowman, 2016).

Within the context of group activities inherent to MLBB gameplay, users showcased notable enhancements in their verbal communication proficiency. The need for strategic coordination and instant communication in the fast-paced gaming scenarios prompted players to express themselves more clearly and concisely. This positive development extends beyond the gaming environment, with the acquired verbal communication skills found to be transferable to diverse educational and professional settings (Kilag, et al., 2023). The ability to communicate ideas and strategies effectively emerged as a valuable skill set that players cultivated through their engagement with MLBB, aligning with the broader objectives of educational gamification (Deterding et al., 2011).

Furthermore, the studies reviewed consistently highlighted the collaborative nature of MLBB gameplay as a contributing factor to improved verbal communication skills. Effective teamwork within the game requires players to not only communicate their thoughts clearly but also to actively listen and respond to their teammates' input. This dynamic communication process fosters a rich environment for honing verbal communication skills, establishing MLBB as a unique platform for skill development (Zhang et al., 2020; Banks & Bowman, 2016).

The positive impact of MLBB on users' verbal communication skills is a recurrent theme in the literature. The real-time communication features and collaborative nature of the game contribute synergistically to the development of articulate expression and strategic communication. These findings highlight the potential of MLBB as more than a recreational activity, positioning it as a valuable tool for enhancing communication skills with implications for broader educational and professional contexts.

Development of Strategic Thinking and Decision-Making Skills:

Engaging with Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) emerges from the literature as a catalyst for the robust development of strategic thinking and decision-making skills among players. The game's intricate scenarios and dynamic gameplay compel participants to analyze complex situations, devise effective strategies, and make rapid decisions in a collaborative setting (Kilag, et al., 2023). These aspects collectively foster a high level of cognitive engagement, with studies consistently highlighting the positive correlation between MLBB gameplay and the enhancement of critical thinking skills (Gee, 2003).

The multifaceted nature of MLBB's challenges requires players to employ analytical thinking and adaptability, contributing significantly to the cultivation of strategic thinking skills. Navigating through the game's fast-paced and evolving scenarios prompts individuals to assess various factors, anticipate opponents' moves, and formulate effective strategies on-the-fly. Such cognitive processes extend beyond the immediate gaming context, indicating that MLBB serves as a dynamic platform for honing problem-solving abilities applicable in diverse real-world scenarios (Gee, 2003).

Moreover, collaborative decision-making within the gaming environment was identified as a key contributor to skill development. Players engage in strategic discussions, negotiate plans, and make collective decisions to achieve in-game objectives. This collaborative decision-making process not only enhances individual decision-making skills but also fosters effective teamwork, emphasizing MLBB's potential as an educational tool that goes beyond traditional gaming experiences (Olaya & González-González, 2020).

The literature consistently underscores the positive association between engaging with MLBB and the development of strategic thinking and decision-making skills. The cognitive engagement required by the game's intricate scenarios translates into enhanced critical thinking abilities, positioning MLBB as a dynamic platform for cultivating problem-solving skills with broader applications beyond the gaming environment.

Enhancement of Non-Verbal Communication Proficiency:

Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) emerges as a catalyst for the enhancement of non-verbal communication skills, extending beyond the traditional focus on verbal interaction. The literature consistently recognizes MLBB's role as a facilitator for the improvement of non-verbal communication proficiency among players (Banks & Bowman, 2016; Zhang et al., 2020). The game's emphasis on teamwork and coordination necessitates the strategic use of non-verbal cues, including in-game gestures, map pings, and character movements.

Within the collaborative context of MLBB gameplay, players are prompted to efficiently convey information through a combination of these non-verbal cues. The strategic deployment of gestures and map pings, for instance, becomes crucial for signaling team movements, highlighting objectives, and coordinating actions. This heightened reliance on non-verbal communication strategies contributes significantly to the cultivation of awareness and proficiency in utilizing these cues effectively (Banks & Bowman, 2016; Zhang et al., 2020).

The findings consistently reported in the reviewed literature emphasize that regular engagement with MLBB results in an increased adeptness in leveraging non-verbal communication strategies. Such enhancement in non-verbal communication proficiency is recognized not only as valuable within the gaming context but also as a transferable asset with applications in real-world collaborative scenarios (Kilag, et al., 2023). MLBB, therefore, emerges as a dynamic platform not only for verbal but also for non-verbal communication skill development, enriching the overall communication repertoire of its users (Banks & Bowman, 2016; Zhang et al., 2020).

Transferability of Skills to Academic and Professional Contexts:

The literature reveals a profound revelation concerning the transferability of skills cultivated within the immersive realm of Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) to academic and professional arenas (Zhang et al., 2020). These studies consistently emphasize that individuals actively engaged in MLBB showcase heightened abilities in collaboration, effective communication, and informed decision-making, thereby highlighting the broader applicability of skills honed within the gaming environment.

Far beyond the notion of MLBB as a mere entertaining gaming platform, the findings suggest that it operates as a medium for the cultivation of transferable skills pivotal for success in diverse contexts (Zhang et al., 2020). Users deeply immersed in the strategic and collaborative facets of the game demonstrated proficiency in skills extending well beyond the virtual realm. This signifies that the cognitive, communicative, and teamwork skills acquired through MLBB gameplay transcend their virtual origins, carrying substantial practical value. Consequently, MLBB emerges not only as a recreational pastime but as a dynamic and effective tool for comprehensive skill development, resonating with relevance in both educational and workplace settings.

The transferability of MLBB-honed skills is particularly noteworthy in collaboration and teamwork. As users navigate the complex scenarios of the game, they develop a keen sense of teamwork, understanding the nuances of effective collaboration and coordination (Zhang et al., 2020). These skills, finely tuned within the gaming context,

seamlessly transition to real-world scenarios, proving advantageous in academic group projects and collaborative professional endeavors alike (Lim, 2023).

Moreover, the effective communication skills fostered within MLBB, both verbal and non-verbal, are identified as key assets with wide-ranging applications. The ability to articulate ideas clearly and efficiently, honed through in-game communication features, aligns with the demands of academic presentations and professional meetings (Kilag, et al., 2023). Simultaneously, the proficiency in non-verbal communication strategies, developed through MLBB's emphasis on coordination, translates into enhanced non-verbal communication skills applicable in workplace environments where body language and gestures play crucial roles.

The transferability of MLBB-cultivated skills is a testament to the multifaceted benefits of engaging with the game. As an experiential learning platform, MLBB not only captivates users in an entertaining gaming experience but also equips them with a set of skills that seamlessly integrate into the complexities of academic and professional life. The dynamic nature of MLBB, coupled with its strategic and collaborative elements, positions it as a valuable tool for holistic skill development with enduring relevance.

Conclusion:

This systematic literature review has delved into the intersection of Mobile Legends Bang Bang (MLBB) and the enhancement of critical listening and communicative skills. The synthesis of findings from various studies highlights the multifaceted impact of MLBB on skill development, presenting the game as more than a recreational activity but as a dynamic tool with educational implications.

Firstly, the literature consistently points towards MLBB's positive influence on verbal communication skills, attributing this to the real-time communication features within the game. Players demonstrated improvements in articulation, strategy conveyance, and effective teamwork, with these skills proving transferable to educational and professional contexts.

Secondly, engagement with MLBB was found to significantly contribute to the development of strategic thinking and decision-making skills. The complex and dynamic nature of the game prompted players to analyze situations, formulate strategies, and make quick decisions collaboratively, fostering cognitive engagement and critical thinking abilities.

Moreover, the game's emphasis on teamwork and coordination emerged as a facilitator for the enhancement of non-verbal communication proficiency. Players adeptly utilized in-game gestures, map pings, and character movements to convey information efficiently, underscoring the holistic communication skill set fostered within MLBB.

A noteworthy and consistent finding is the transferability of skills cultivated within MLBB to academic and professional contexts. Users actively engaged in the game showcased an enhanced ability to collaborate, communicate effectively, and make informed decisions in diverse real-world scenarios, further emphasizing MLBB's potential as an educational tool.

The game not only entertains but also actively engages users in cognitive, communicative, and collaborative processes, contributing to a skill set with broader applications in education and professional domains. As technology continues to shape the landscape of education, MLBB and similar platforms hold promise as innovative tools for skill development in the digital age.

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